

Progress and lessons learnt from the stakeholder engagement in MULTISOURCE pilot locations (midterm)

Deliverable 6.2

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List of abbreviations

ENTS	Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
NBSWT	Nature-Based Solutions for Water Treatment
LL	Living Lab

Executive Summary

The MULTISOURCE Project aims at advancing Nature-Based Solutions for Water Treatment (NBSWT) by integrating innovative approaches with broader environmental, societal, and policy considerations. Its success relies on the proactive involvement of stakeholders with the technical Pilots and Tools developed within the framework of the project, guided through the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework.

This report provides an overview of a 15-month progress snapshot, providing insights for stakeholders, researchers, and practitioners in the water treatment landscape. The focus of this report is on the implementation of the MULTISOURCE Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework, underscoring stakeholder engagement through co-design activities, decision-making tools, and the establishment of a Living Lab. This framework systematically guides the identification, analysis, and strategy development for diverse stakeholders, ensuring effective processes in technical Pilots and tool development.

The Road Map, as introduced in this report, serves as a structured guide for the implementation of the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework, supporting the Pilot and Tool leads to outline objectives, roles, and responsibilities for engaging with the relevant stakeholders. Pilot leads, with support from partners such as ICLEI, concentrate on identifying benefits/impacts, monitoring ENTS Pilots, and co-designing water treatment processes and business models/tools. The Living Lab in Girona emphasizes community co-creation and validation of tools, while expert groups in Milan and Grand Lyon contribute specialised insights. The roadmap structure includes an introduction, long-term and short-term objectives, and a timeline. The Stakeholder Engagement Activity Overview Table supports the strategic planning of each activity, linking activities to project milestones, ensuring alignment with goals for effective implementation.

Over 15 months, stakeholder engagement in the MULTISOURCE Project has been centred on NBSWT Pilots, involving local, regional, and national authorities, the community, civil society, the private sector, and academia. Utilising methods such as expert group roundtables, interviews, virtual dialogues, workshops, field visits, and visualisations enhances dialogue, gathers insights, and fosters effective communication. This comprehensive approach ensures the development of collaborative, innovative, and resilient NBSWT, while promoting knowledge exchange in an inclusive manner.

The key lessons from these initial stakeholder activities underscore successful strategies like interactive exercises, group discussions, and field visits. The Expert Group Roundtable and workshops prove effective, though challenges include time constraints in virtual engagements and diverse stakeholder expertise. The key highlights emphasise the importance of in-person discussions, flexible engagement strategies, and realistic goal setting for fruitful collaboration in water treatment initiatives.

Taking into consideration the lessons learned, this report suggests some best practices for future stakeholder engagement: utilising collaborative work tools, building a knowledge base through knowledge sharing, tailoring strategies to stakeholders' mandates, encouraging cross-sector collaboration, promoting pre-engagement participation, incorporating capacity-building activities, diversifying engagement formats, fostering inclusive decision-making, investing in long-term relationships, and establishing a feedback mechanism for continuous improvement. These ideas aim to enhance transparency, relevance, and effectiveness in future stakeholder engagements in nature-based solutions for water treatment.

Introduction

MULTISOURCE focuses on integrating Nature-Based Solutions for Water Treatment (NBSWT) with the domains of environment, circular economy, society, and policy. Key to this approach is active engagement with stakeholders, defined as those impacted by, possessing relevant information for, interested in, or influenced by the outcomes. The stakeholder engagement focuses on the development and monitoring of the [Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions \(ENTS\) Pilots](#), the creation of business models and planning tools, and at later stages on assessing the benefits of such solutions for water treatment. The Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions within MULTISOURCE refers to a subset of NBSWT with enhanced treatment capacity, cost-effectiveness, and/or reduced environmental impact compared to conventional alternatives.

Engaging stakeholders is critical to advancing the development of innovative nature-based solutions for water management and treatment, seamlessly integrating them into comprehensive, long-term planning strategies. This collaborative approach not only fosters the development of informed and relevant policies but also supports the combination of these innovative solutions alongside traditional grey infrastructure. To achieve these objectives, it is important to incorporate a diverse array of stakeholders, ensuring their involvement is timely and meaningful.

To achieve such goals, the partners involved in the MULTISOURCE project have adopted the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework. This framework involves mapping, analysing, and prioritising relevant actors associated with the development and monitoring of ENTS Pilots. Through this strategic approach, stakeholders are not only invited to provide valuable feedback but has also been informed about the latest scientific advancements through evidence-based outcomes for water treatment.

By fostering collaboration among practitioners, relevant departments of local and regional authorities, and other stakeholders, the MULTISOURCE project aims to drive the adoption of these Nature-based Solutions in policy and planning documents. The key objective is to ensure the seamless integration of the innovative approaches and established grey infrastructure, ensuring sustainable and effective water management and treatment solutions in the urban areas.

This report aims to present a comprehensive overview of the methodology for the implementation of the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework, referred from now onwards in the text as "the Road Map" It delves into the ongoing progress of implementing the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework and conducts an initial assessment of activities and insights gained from stakeholder engagement in the realm of water treatment across seven technical Pilots in the MULTISOURCE project.

Finally, the report offers preliminary reflections on both the successful elements and challenges encountered during the engagement with diverse stakeholders. The intention is to refine and enhance the stakeholder engagement process throughout the remaining duration of the project, concluding in May 2025. The report shares some valuable lessons learned over the past 15 months, shedding light on activities undertaken by project partners in collaboration with local stakeholders. By doing so, the report will provide insights for fellow practitioners and researchers engaged in stakeholder engagement for water treatment initiatives.

1. Implementation Overview

This chapter provides a detailed overview of the development of the Road Map, which structure aims to stimulate meaningful engagement with relevant stakeholders throughout the project's journey. The primary focus of this facilitation extends to co-design activities, specifically involving the creation of tools such as decision-making tools, planning platform, and business models, including the monitoring of technical Pilots and the establishment of the Living Lab alongside with the Pilot in Girona.

Figure 1. Context for the stakeholder engagement within MULTISOURCE Project

2. Stakeholder Identification and Analysis

The involvement of diverse stakeholders in the monitoring, evaluation of the technical Pilots, and the development of ENTS and Tools highlight the need for the establishment of effective and inclusive processes. Addressing this requirement, the MULTISOURCE project employs the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework, serving as a comprehensive guide for stakeholder interactions. This framework is structured into three main sections: I) understanding the purpose of engagement, II) analysing stakeholder categories, and III) developing the strategy and methods for engagement.

The framework aims to achieve outcomes including, defining engagement purposes, identifying suitable stakeholder groups, and developing effective engagement strategies for them.

The diagram in Figure 2, provides an overview of the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework. A more comprehensive and detailed report of this framework is [available here](#).

Figure 2. Co-design framework for stakeholder engagement

3. Road Map Structure

The Road Map, a planning guide, is put together and aims to steer the Development and the monitoring of ENTS in the technical Pilots, and the creation of business models and tools. This Road Map covers both short and long-term perspectives. The short-term plan, covering annual periods like 2022-2023 and beyond, outlines specific activities. For the short term (2022-2023), the plan puts the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework in use by providing a clear outline for activities within that timeframe. Meanwhile, the long-term plan (2022-2025 in the case of the MULTISOURCE project) outlines strategic goals for each Pilot and tool, guiding subsequent activities and stakeholder engagement. This approach helps the technical Pilot Leads to organise their work and understand the necessary steps for

engaging with the stakeholders. Pilot and Tool leads update and develop annual short-term plans to ensure they stay on track and achieve or adapt their objectives.

3.1. Objectives of the Road Map

The Road Map serves as a structured guide for MULTISOURCE project partners, offering a systematic approach to map and implement stakeholder engagement activities. Additionally, this Road Map serves as the framework to delineate key outputs and emphasize the strategic aspects of both Pilots and Tools. These strategic elements, outlined in the Road Map, play a critical role in directing and informing the stakeholder engagement activities throughout the project.

3.2. Roles and responsibilities of the Pilot Leads: Development and implementation of the Road Map

All partners leading the design and monitoring of the ENTS in the technical Pilots and Tools, with support from other partners such as ICLEI, shall develop the Road Map that outlines the stakeholder engagement activities related to the following project activities:

- Identification of the potential benefits/ negative impact of the Pilots and Tools
- Identification of indicators/methods to monitor the ENTS Pilots.
- Co-design processes for water treatment
- Co-development of Business Models/ Tools

In addition to the above-mentioned activities, when developing the Road Map, the respective project partners from the Living Lab in Girona, the Milan Metropolitan Area & Grand Lyon Metropolitan Area should take into consideration the following aspects:

Girona Living Lab

- Build on the co-creation of the Living Lab community garden.
- Test and validate the business models and tools.
- Share their experiences and lessons learned with the other partners within the MULTISOURCE projects, stakeholders, and practitioners.

Milan Metropolitan Area & Grand Lyon

- Set up and convene expert groups.

4. Content of the Road Map for stakeholder engagement implementation

This section outlines the structure of the Road Map that Pilot leads have used as a guide to develop their strategy for implementing stakeholder engagement in their respective Pilots. The Road Map is intended to be a clear and concise document, providing essential information on the long- and short-term planning of key activities and the expected outcomes during stakeholder engagement.

4.1. Introduction to the Road Map

The Road Map introduction offers a brief overview of the document, outlining key activities planned by each Pilot team. This concise description, limited to around one paragraph, aims to inform the reader, and serve as an introduction to the Road Map, providing a snapshot of the planned developments.

4.2. Main purpose of the stakeholder engagement

The main purpose of engaging with the key group(s) of stakeholders will be translated into the Road Map on the long-term and short-term objectives. The development of the long and short-term objectives of the activities each Pilot/ Tool plan to undertake will be in accordance with the main outputs they will deliver by the end of the project. The following questions will support the Pilot/ Tool leaders to develop

their objectives for the Road Map. It is suggested the short-term objectives to be developed on an annual basis in order to take into consideration the latest developments in the projects as well as the lessons learned from the previous stakeholder engagement activities. This approach ensures flexibility to revise previous short-term objectives as needed.

Long-Term Planning (2022-2025 for the MULTISOURCE project)

- What are the key objectives during the MULTISOURCE lifetime for your Pilot/ Tool?
- What are the expected outcomes, your Pilot/ Tool aims to produce during the project lifetime?

Short-Term Planning (2022-2023 for the MULTISOURCE project)

- What are the key objectives during the period Dec. 2022 – Dec. 2023?
- What are the expected outcomes your Pilot/ Tool aims to produce within this period?

4.3. Timeline of the Activities

In order to ensure the achievement of the short-term and eventually the long-term objectives for the stakeholder engagement it is important to develop the timeline, horizontal arrow with yearly and monthly (if needed) intervals marked by vertical lines, of the activities envisioned in the short -term and the long- term. The timeline of the activities it is not an exhaustive list of activities, but it can be revised and updated periodically.

Long term Planning 2022-2025

In the case of MULTISOURCE project, the starting point of this timeline is Dec. 2022 till end of the project in May 2025. Within this timeframe the most important elements that are indicated are as follows:

- Project Consortium Meetings (occurring annually)-PM
- Main Outputs/ Deliverables/ Milestones (visualise the timeframe of the activity) - Mx
- Potential strategic moments to engage with relevant stakeholders (pin the activity on the month to be delivered) – Stakeholder Engagement

Mx: Main Outputs/ Deliverables/ Milestones
Stakeholder Engagement: Envisaged moments for engagement related to the Mx
PM: Project Meeting

Figure 3. Template of the long-term planning timeline

Short Term Planning 2022-2023

For the short-term planning, for example, for the period 2022-2023, the timeframe is Nov 2022 - Dec 2023. For the development of this part, the Pilot/ Tool lead is focusing on outlining the most important interactions with the relevant groups of stakeholders in order to achieve the short-term objectives. Within this timeframe the most important elements that are indicated are as follows:

- Annual Project Meeting
- Main Outputs/ Deliverables/ Milestones (pin the activity on the month to be delivered)
- Envisaged moments to engage with the relevant stakeholders linked to the above-mentioned outputs.

Figure 4. Template of the short-term planning timeline

In the Annex 1 you may find some examples of the timelines developed from the technical Pilots of the MULTISOURCE project.

To ensure the seamless implementation of planned activities, Pilot/Tool leads, and their teams can utilize the following table (see Table 1) as a helpful resource. The Stakeholder Engagement Activity Overview Table is a strategic planning tool designed to assist Pilot/Tool leads and their teams in effectively conceptualizing and implementing stakeholder engagement. Moreover, this table serves as a tool to assist partners in aligning their initiatives with the short-term project activities, as well as the project's primary outputs.

It comprises several key sections:

- Introduction to the Stakeholder Engagement Activity
- Link to Project's Milestone/Deliverables
- Context of the engagement activity (Why – Who – How)
- Timeline for the activity preparation and implementation
- Organisational Logistic of the activity

The following table serves as a user-friendly guide, facilitating a structured approach to developing stakeholder engagement activities while ensuring alignment with the overall project goals. By proactively developing the concept for each stakeholder engagement activity, Pilot/Tool leads gain a comprehensive understanding of the required resources, planning timeline, and effort involved. This systematic approach enables them to evaluate the feasibility of each activity and effectively manage its preparation and implementation.

Introduction to the stakeholder engagement activity	Title of the activity			
	<i>[Add the title of the activity]</i>			
	Short description of the activity (max 60 words)			
<i>[Add a short description of the envisioned stakeholder activity]</i>				
Link to the Milestone/ Deliverables of the project	Title of the Milestone/ Deliverable/Main Output			
	<i>[Add the title of the Milestone or Deliverable the above-mentioned activity is linked to.]</i>			
	Short description of the Milestones/ Deliverables/Main Outputs (max 60 words)			
<i>[Add a short description of the Milestone/ Deliverable the above-mentioned activity is linked to.]</i>				
Co-design Framework for stakeholder engagement (Available here)	Purpose for stakeholder engagement			
	<i>[Please select one of the following categories and specify the purpose of engagement on your context]</i>			
	<i>Documentation of the lessons learned</i>	<i>Sharing of knowledge and experience</i>	<i>Integration of experts' views</i>	<i>Evaluation of outcomes and outputs</i>
	Group(s) of the stakeholders (Please consult the Stakeholder Engagement Process (i.e., Miro Boards) for your Pilot/ Tool)			
	<i>[Add the group of stakeholders you plan to involve in the engagement activity, e.g., practitioners, water utility departments, water body group, etc.]</i>			
	Method to engage			
<i>[Add the methods of engagement, e.g., Workshop, Field trip, session in the conference, etc.]</i>				
Timeline (See above)	Period to engage with the stakeholders (Month)			
	<i>[Consult the above the timeline you have developed, mention the month or if possible, the exact date(s) of the stakeholder engagement activity]</i>			

Logistics of the organisation	Leading organisation to develop the stakeholder engagement activity		
	<i>[Add the name of the organisation which is leading the stakeholder engagement activity]</i>		
	Potential synergies with other project partners		
	<i>[Add the name of the organisation which you seek collaboration for the preparation and implementation of the stakeholder engagement activity]</i>		
	Support from ICLEI [Please select the level of support from ICLEI and specify it based on your context]		
	Basic: Inform ICLEI on the activity development	Intermediate: Consult ICLEI on the activity development	Advanced: Co-develop the activity
	Local/ Regional/ International Event to organise the stakeholder engagement activity as part of it		
	<i>[Add the name of the bigger event under which the stakeholder engagement activity is taking place]</i>		

Table 1. Detail information for the stakeholder engagement activity

5. Progress Update - Short Term Progress (2022 - 2023)

5.1. Overview of progress made in stakeholder engagement

WHY - PURPOSE OF ENGAGEMENT

- Sharing of knowledge & experience
- Integration of experts' views, needs of target end users
- Documentation of the lessons learned

WHO - GROUPS OF STAKEHOLDERS

National/ Regional, Local authorities, various departments of municipalities, academia, private sector & civil society.

HOW - METHODS OF ENGAGEMENT

- Expert Group Round-table
- Workshop
- Interview

THE MAIN OBJECTIVES OF THE ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITY

- Establish collaborative relationships, align visions, and achieve common goals to implement and promote NBSWT.
- Share experiences, address challenges, and introduce innovative NBSWT.
- Enabling conditions for the co-funding & co-benefits of NBSWT.

KEY HIGHLIGHTS

- Presentation of the MULTISOURCE results, address implementation issues in technical, governance, and business aspects.
- Positive feedback & interest in collaborative work for innovative yet practical solutions.
- Identification of challenges with current regulations and guidelines, identified barriers and drivers for wider adoption of NBSWT.

LESSONS LEARNED

- Context specific and realistic goals are crucial to initiate discussions effectively.
- Positive response likely influenced by the maturity of the NBSWT subject in the Pilot areas.
- Diverse representation of stakeholders (research, authorities, administration, etc.) leads to engaging and insightful discussions.
- High level of interest indicates the opportune moment for raising NBSWT discussions.

GOOD PRACTICES

- Introductory presentations for a comprehensive knowledge base.
- Round-table sessions encourage collaborative discussions and exchange of diverse viewpoints.
- Shared work tools allow for written records of results and discussions, ensuring clarity and accountability.

Figure 5 Common Calendar of the stakeholder engagement activities in the technical Pilots

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101003527.

5.2. Why- Purpose of engagement

Over the past 15 months, the Pilot/Tool leads have successfully implemented a series of stakeholder engagement activities, showcasing a commitment to collaboration and knowledge exchange. Engaging stakeholders unfolds as an integral aspect (see Picture 5) of the Nature-Based Solutions for Water Treatment (NBSWT) Pilots in MULTISOURCE project. The approach encompasses diverse activities aimed at fostering collaboration, sharing expertise, and aligning visions for a more impactful implementation. The purpose of the stakeholder engagement activity has been clustered as follows:

Figure 6. Purpose of engaging with the stakeholders, in the MULTISOURCE Pilots

Evaluation of Outcomes and Outputs from the Pilots

In the case of the technology selection tool, the presentation and validation of the structure and content stands as an important step for the seamless integration of such a tool in the private market of water treatment technologies as well as supporting the tool to have capacity to support several available technologies used for the water treatment and management. This ensures transparency and collective validation, fostering a sense of ownership among stakeholders in the private sector.

Showcasing the key outcomes for the indicator selection to measure the impact of the NBSWT underscores the importance to inclusivity and acceptance in the co-creation of the monitoring system of the NBSWT from the community. By sharing these outcomes with the local authorities and the communities, it is also accompanied with an invitation for constructive feedback, fostering continuous improvement of the key set of indicators that will be used by the end- users.

Integration of Experts' Views

Demonstrating the tools developed in the context of MULTISOURCE project and seeking feedback, ensures the tool's relevance and effectiveness, through an iterative refinement process based on expert insights.

Discussions and validations of both the workflow and graphical interface of the technology selection tool foster the co-creation, ensuring alignment with practical needs and expectations of experts.

Integration of Views and Needs of Target End Users

Conducting interviews with urban actors to understand their mandates, priorities, pains, and gains is a necessary step in order to develop business models that can support the up-scaling of the NBSWT methods as well as to accelerate the up-take of these solutions from the local and regional authorities. Furthermore, this knowledge informs initiatives and paves the way for strategic partnerships and co-financing opportunities.

Planning the green wall installation, in the case of the Living Lab in Girona, represents a hands-on commitment both from the technical Pilot and the local community. Evaluating potential challenges demonstrates foresight and a proactive approach, ensuring a smoother execution process and the

acceptance of the project from the wider community. Moreover, the process of selecting indicators for the Menja't Sant Narcís community garden in Girona reflects dedication to measurable impact. Involving stakeholders in this decision-making ensures that impact assessments align with their priorities and fosters the sense of ownership for this project.

Sharing of Knowledge and Experience:

The workshop organised by the city of Oslo in collaboration with NIVA focused on knowledge sharing. By adopting a comprehensive agenda of presenting the Nordic experience and requirements related to treatment of storm water, identifying challenges with the state of art of the tools available, and introducing new solutions demonstrate a proactive approach in contributing to a collective learning journey with a wide group of stakeholders representing local and regional authorities, academia and the private sector. Moreover, by raising awareness on the innovative ENTS for water treatment enhances the chances from the stakeholder and the respective organisations to up-scale such solutions or integrate them in strategic documents.

Making personal contact with city members and sharing expertise emphasises a relational approach. Acknowledging the need to engage diverse stakeholders highlights an understanding that sustainable solutions require multidiscipline collaborations. Navigating this dynamic landscape, these reflections guide toward an even more impactful and harmonised journey in the realm of Nature-Based Solutions for Water Treatment.

5.3. Who? - Groups of the engaged stakeholders

In the evolving landscape of governance and community development, the effective collaboration among the different scales of government, academia, and the private sector has emerged as a vital force in shaping policies and initiatives. This chapter provides an overview of the different groups of stakeholders that were engaged in the different engagement activities that were organised by the NBSWT Pilot leads with the local stakeholders.

The diagram below shows an overview of the categories of stakeholders engaged in the different activities from the technical Pilots and Tools.

Figure 7 Groups of the engaged stakeholders.

Collaboration Dynamics: Local, Regional and National Authorities

The regional authority serves as a nexus connecting national authorities, local authorities, and other governance structures such as associations of municipalities (i.e., the administration of Nordic

municipalities), academia, and the private sector. In this collaborative network, it is important to engage the regional authorities, for fostering a holistic understanding of regional challenges and opportunities. National authorities contribute to overarching policies, while local authorities and municipalities offer on-the-ground insights.

The multidisciplinary interaction and exchange between regional water authorities, local authorities, the private sector, civil society organizations, and academia ensures that data is not confined within silos but is shared and utilized for comprehensive decision-making processes.

Local authorities play a pivotal role in a multidisciplinary collaboration to address matters such as water treatment. They act as intermediaries between regional bodies and communities. The collaboration involves not only the exchange of knowledge with other administrative bodies such as the water authorities, the private sector, and civil society organizations but also includes academia, which contributes specialized knowledge and innovative approaches.

Grassroots Engagement: Local Community and Civil Society

At the community level, the collaboration for water treatment with NbS extends beyond formal structures to involve the community directly. The input from the community is considered invaluable, creating a two-way flow of information that enriches the decision-making process. This approach not only empowers the community with knowledge, but also lays the foundation for future collaborations by nurturing a data-literate generation. Finally, on the governance aspect this collaboration ensures that policies related to water treatment are not only effective but also resonate with the needs and aspirations of the local communities that are affected by the implementation of the water treatment projects.

Catalysts for Innovation: Private Sector and Academia

The private sector and academia serve as catalysts for innovation in the landscape of water treatment with nature-based solutions. Their involvement brings cutting-edge technologies, research outcomes, and expertise to the table. The collaboration with regional and local authorities, as well as the community, creates a synergy for a more systemic approach for water treatment in the local or regional level. Nurturing such relationships, innovative approaches can flow easier in the market, allowing the private sector to keep up to speed with the needs of the cities and their people.

In conclusion, the effective collaboration among regional authorities, local authorities, the community, private sector, and academia creates a robust framework for the utilization of the NBSWT. This collaborative approach not only ensures the efficient exchange of knowledge but also promotes inclusivity, innovation, and resilience of the key community systems.

5.4. How? – Methods and tools in stakeholder engagement.

During the stakeholder engagement process, the methods and tools played an important role in shaping the dialogue, extracting meaningful insights, and fostering effective communication. This chapter explores the diverse array of methods and tools utilized across various settings, ranging from expert group roundtables to virtual workshops and conferences.

Figure 8 Methods and tools in stakeholder engagement

Experts Group Roundtable

The Experts Group Roundtable, as set in the Metropolitan Area of Milan, serves as a cornerstone for in-depth discussions, leveraging the multidisciplinary group of participants to provide different perspectives on the realm of the water treatment as well as to raise awareness for innovative approaches such as the ENTS and their integration in the urban-regional landscape. This method includes a structured approach, ensuring that key insights are not only shared verbally but also captured and guide the next steps of the experts' discussions.

On the one hand, the workshop format implemented in multidisciplinary groups, encourages participants to be exposed in diverse perspectives, fostering a rich exchange of ideas. The use of presentations, moderation materials further enhance the interactive nature of these sessions.

On the other hand, plenary discussions brought together stakeholders from various backgrounds for comprehensive dialogues. These sessions aimed to align diverse viewpoints and ensure that decisions reflected a collective vision. The combination of expert insights, on-the-ground experiences from the relevant departments in the municipality, and community perspectives enriches the discussion and informs the decision-making process.

Interviews - Virtual Dialogues

Virtual communication platforms are instrumental for the interview methodology, when in person interaction is not feasible. The virtual setting enables seamless communication, while the recording function, if consented from all the participants, preserves the details of the conversation for future referencing and reporting purposes. This method allows to reach to several groups that might not be easily reachable otherwise to share their perspectives and their experiences in the realm of the water treatment with nature-based solutions. In the case of MULTISOURCE this method of engagement was deployed to reach out to several actors (e.g., regional water authority, local authority, private sector, civil society organisation, etc.) for creating a comprehensive understanding of the mandates, priorities, pains, gains of urban actors who could co-finance NBSWT.

Visualizing Connections

Online Workshop

The integration of virtual conference (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams etc.) and interactive platforms (e.g., Miro, Mural, etc.) transforms virtual workshops into visually engaging experiences, as they provide an overview of flows and connections formed during the workshop. This method adds a layer of depth to the collaborative process by visualizing relationships and networks. Participants engage in real-time collaboration, fostering creativity and innovation. The visual nature of such platforms adds a dynamic dimension to workshops, enhancing the overall online experience of the stakeholders engaged in the activity.

On site Workshop

The onsite workshops that were implemented from the MULTISOURCE partners adopt a more tactile approach utilise posters, post-its, and printed cards. This hands-on method encourages participants to physically engage with ideas, impacts, and indicators. The tangible nature of this approach fosters a sense of connection and ownership among participants. Defining the next action points for interaction forms a dynamic and varied landscape for the exploration and exchange of ideas.

Field Visits

Field visits are proven instrumental in grounding the project in the reality of its environment. By visiting the Pilots such as the school in Girona and engaging directly with stakeholders on-site, the project team gained valuable insights into the local context. This method facilitated a multidimensional understanding of the project's potential impacts and challenges. The combination of this method to with one of the

above-mentioned methods, creates a more comprehensive approach of stakeholder engagement process, by linking the discussions with on – ground experience.

6. Navigating the Landscape of Stakeholder Engagement: Key highlights & Lessons Learned

Stakeholder engagement is a cornerstone in the success of any project for water management with ENTs, and as this report explores the activities, challenges, and lessons learned from the engagement process, a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play emerges.

The MULTISOURCE project with the implementation of the Co-design Stakeholder Engagement Framework aims to initiate conversations among key actors involved in the field of water management, with a focus on presenting project results from the implementation and monitoring of the ENTs developed in the Pilots and to receive feedback on the development of the tools. The feedback received indicated a shared interest in bringing innovation to the forefront, balanced with a critical and realistic perspective.

6.1. Key Highlights from the stakeholder engagement activity

Greywater- Girona, Spain

- Technology: Wet Wall: Hybrid living wall
- Challenge addressed: Climate adaptation, citizen engagement, risk assessment, urban farming.
- Main innovation: Use of digital tools, promote citizen engagement; ecosystem services assessment.

The inclusion of interactive exercises in workshops proved to be a successful strategy for fostering engagement. Icebreakers, group discussions, and collaborative exercises encouraged participants to share their perspectives openly about the development of the green wall and the monitoring system. This interactive approach not only enhanced communication but also built a sense of ownership for the project among stakeholders.

One notable outcome was the selection of a comprehensive list of indicators to measure the impacts of interest. Stakeholders collaboratively identified key metrics and criteria that would be crucial in evaluating the success of the project. This list served as a foundation for monitoring and evaluation processes moving forward.

The engagement activities also brought to light multiple views on the necessity of monitoring impacts. While some stakeholders emphasized the importance of monitoring to ensure accountability and effectiveness, others expressed concerns about potential burdens on local communities. Balancing these perspectives became a key objective for the project team.

The visit to schools and subsequent group discussions emerged as a pivotal milestone in the engagement process. It facilitated the interchange of technical information, enabling the project team to address specific concerns raised by the community. This direct interaction strengthened the project's foundation by building trust and transparency with key stakeholders.

In conclusion, the stakeholder engagement activities played a crucial role in shaping the project's direction. The combination of workshops, expert roundtables, field visits, and plenary discussions ensured a holistic and inclusive approach to decision-making. The key highlights underscore the importance of ongoing dialogue, collaboration, and adaptability as the project progresses.

Raw Wastewater – Metropolitan Area of Milan

- Technology: Rhizosph'air aerated french wetland
- Challenge addressed: Simultaneous treatment of solids and wastewater; extreme rain events.

- Main innovation: Compact (<1m²/PE*), new design guidance; innovative/ICT monitoring approaches

The Expert Group Roundtable provided an ideal setting to comprehensively present the ENTS that is being developed by the technical partner. This included an overview of the current status, ongoing initiatives, and future goals. The stakeholders gained a holistic understanding of the technical Pilot's scope and potential impact.

To ensure a systematic approach, the engagement was organized around three key themes: technical, governance, and business. This allowed for an in-depth exploration of specific challenges and opportunities within each domain, facilitating a more nuanced and targeted discussion.

One of the primary objectives of the roundtable was to identify and address key issues impeding the smooth implementation of ENTS in the Metropolitan Area of Milan. Through collaborative discussions, stakeholders actively contributed to the identification of challenges and proposed potential solutions. This participatory approach fostered a sense of ownership among the stakeholders.

The engagement activities received positive feedback from the participating stakeholders. There was interest expressed in collaboratively working towards innovation. The stakeholders acknowledged the critical and realistic approach taken by the project team, appreciating the balance between ambitious goals and the practicalities of implementation. This mutual understanding laid the foundation for a more grounded and achievable implementation strategy.

The round-table discussions pave the way for shared work and collaborative innovation. Stakeholders expressed a willingness to contribute their expertise and resources to advance the project. This collaborative spirit can enable the upscaling of the ENTS, emphasizing the importance of building a network of support and expertise at the regional level.

The Expert Group Roundtable emerged as a valuable method for stakeholder engagement, providing a structured platform for discussion. The insights gained from this engagement will play a pivotal role in shaping the next phases of the technical Pilot.

Road Runoff, Oslo, Norway

- Technology: Raingarden, water-treatment, storage and potential irrigation
- Challenge addressed: Improved water quality for local sea-trout habitat and potential reuse for irrigation.
- Main innovation: Exploring possibilities for alternative water sources for irrigating urban green areas. Demonstrating the use of innovative sorption materials for water treatment.

The participants engaged in group discussions, addressing the challenges posed by existing regulations and guidelines. Gaps and ambiguities in the regulatory framework were identified, providing a comprehensive understanding of hurdles faced.

Part of the workshop focused on the efficacy of follow-up procedures. Stakeholders brainstormed solutions and strategies for streamlining follow-up processes, ensuring active resolution of concerns raised during the workshop.

The formation of breakout sessions allowed participants to explore barriers hindering the uptake of NBSWT. Simultaneously, discussions covered drivers that could incentivise and promote NBSWT, offering a balanced perspective on potential benefits and challenges.

In conclusion, the workshop emerged as a key platform for fostering dialogue and collaboration. By addressing challenges in existing regulations, discussing follow-up procedures, and exploring barriers and drivers for NBSWT adoption, participants gained valuable insights.

Technology Selection Tool

To facilitate meaningful interactions and collaborative discussions, two main methods of engagement were utilised, workshops and attendance to conferences. Workshops provided an informal setting for in-depth discussions, while conferences allowed for a broader exchange of ideas. This dual approach ensured capturing perspectives from diverse stakeholders in the in the landscape of water treatment.

Stakeholders have consistently highlighted the need to enhance the workflow within the SNAPP tool. The recurring theme centres around streamlining processes, reducing redundancies, and improving the overall user experience. There's a unanimous agreement among stakeholders that these improvements are crucial for optimizing efficiency and creating a more intuitive and user-friendly interface. The emphasis on workflow enhancements reflects a shared commitment to developing a tool that seamlessly aligns with user needs, fostering a more efficient and productive environment.

6.2. Challenges in Engaging with Stakeholders

Engaging with stakeholders proved to be a mixed experience. While most participants showed enthusiasm and interest, there were challenges, particularly with entities that have historically been difficult to engage. Time constraints during virtual webinars posed challenges, emphasizing the need for tailored engagement strategies.

Challenges included the necessity of finding a common vocabulary and overcoming time constraints, with some participants unable to attend the entire workshop. Virtual discussions were noted as less facilitating, pointing towards the limitations of digital engagement.

Finally, engaging stakeholders not familiar with NBSWT proved challenging due to the high diversity in expertise and needs related to NBS implementation. On site engagement, hands-on activities, and capacity building approaches were highlighted as more effective engagement strategies.

6.3. Lessons Learned from the stakeholder engagement process.

The key reflections from the engagement process within the MULTISOURCE project underscore the significance of in-person discussions and hands-on activities around a table. The stakeholders' preference for face-to-face interactions became evident as individuals expressed interest for collaborative discussions, often enhanced by visual aids such as posters and markers. However, it also became apparent that not all stakeholder groups share the same level of interest, emphasising the need for flexible engagement strategies that can accommodate diverse perspectives.

Moreover, the varying levels of readiness among the Pilots in their work highlights the need of engaging with the local stakeholders at different timelines and intensity. This diversity of the technical Pilots highlighted the importance of recognising and accommodating these differences to foster meaningful engagement. Such adaptability is crucial in ensuring that the MULTISOURCE partners and the stakeholders perceive the value of the engagement process in monitoring the ENTS Pilots or tools.

In addition to these lessons, a key takeaway revolves around the necessity of setting realistic and achievable goals during the stakeholder engagement process. This point highlights the importance of specificity and feasibility in goal setting, contributing to a positive and mature environment conducive to fruitful discussions. Another observation is the positive impact of multidisciplinary round table discussions, bringing together individuals from various backgrounds. This combination was found to enhance discussions, with continuous engagement, relationship-building, and tailoring discussions to stakeholder needs emerging as critical elements for success in the engagement process. Overall, the lessons learned emphasise the need for adaptability, and tailored approaches in stakeholder engagement for water treatment.

7. List of Good Ideas for Future Actions

Documentation and Shared Work Tools: The use collaborative work tools allow for real-time documentation and leaves a written record of results. This ensures transparency and accessibility for all stakeholders to follow up on future activities.

Knowledge Base Building: Kicking off engagement activities with introductory presentations that provide diverse perspectives on the topic, establishes a solid knowledge base for subsequent discussions and round-table sessions.

Targeted Stakeholder Engagement: Tailored engagement strategies based on stakeholders' specific mandates (e.g., water, urban greening, real estate) rather than relying solely on umbrella terms like "nature-based solutions" ensures relevance and resonance with the stakeholders.

Cross-Sector Collaboration: Encouraging collaboration across different sectors (e.g., water, urban greening, real estate) to leverage diverse expertise and perspectives, can lead to innovative solutions and a more comprehensive approach to the topic at hand.

Pre-Engagement Participation: Active participation and engagement with stakeholders before workshops or events help building relationships and prevents the perception of them being an incomer, while fostering a sense of inclusion and collaboration.

Capacity building: Incorporating capacity building activities in explaining results to ensure a clear understanding among stakeholders. By using accessible language, visuals, and interactive methods to convey complex information, it makes it more comprehensive and engaging for diverse stakeholders.

Diversify Engagement Formats: By exploring different formats for engagement, such as round-table sessions, workshops, and interactive discussions, this accommodates different learning preferences and ensures that information is communicated effectively to a diverse audience.

Inclusive Decision-Making: It is imperative to foster an inclusive decision-making process by actively seeking input from all stakeholders. It encourages open dialogue, expression of diverse perspectives, and incorporating feedback into decision-making processes.

Long-Term Relationship Building: It is vital to consider engagement as an ongoing process rather than a one-time event. Investing in building long-term relationships with stakeholders, sustains collaboration that yields more meaningful results.

Feedback Mechanism: By establish a feedback mechanism allows stakeholders to provide continuous input and suggestions. This creates a dynamic process where adjustments can be made based on real-time feedback, enhancing the overall effectiveness of future activities.

8. Conclusions: Navigating Towards Project Success

As the Multisource project advances through its interim phase, a comprehensive reflection on key findings, lessons learned, and progress made provides invaluable insights. This conclusion chapter provides the essence of the project's journey, drawing upon the experiences of stakeholder engagements, adaptive strategies, and continuous improvement initiatives.

While the project transitions to the next phase, the focus remains on building resilient partnerships for water treatment. The commitment to continuous improvement positions MULTISOURCE partners as dynamic collaborators ready to address the evolving needs of the local stakeholders. The goal is to create a community of active participants invested in the long-term success of the project.

The insights gained from the first year of the stakeholder co-design framework pave the way for the final phase of the stakeholder engagement in the MULTISOURCE project. The lessons learned serve as guidelines for future engagements, ensuring that the project remains responsive, relevant, and impactful.

The journey towards the final report is characterized by a sense of purpose, collaboration, and a commitment in the realm on water management.

As the ENTS pilots progress, tangible results emerge, providing valuable material to share with local stakeholder groups keen on incorporating innovative water treatment solutions on a full-scale implementation. Each Pilot and Tool's Road Map will undergo updates, incorporating lessons from initial interactions and adjusting short-term and, if necessary, long-term objectives. This adaptive approach ensures ongoing responsiveness to the evolving needs and challenges encountered.

Furthermore, MULTISOURCE partners have now become acquainted with the Co-design Framework, providing them with a comprehensive understanding of the concrete actions required for effective engagement with local stakeholders within the context of their Pilots. In the upcoming phase, they will leverage this familiarity to enhance their interactions and contribute meaningfully to the project's overarching goals.

In conclusion, the interim phase of the MULTISOURCE project has been characterized by thoughtful reflection, flexible adaptation, and an unwavering commitment to constant improvement. Our evolving relationship with stakeholders, the integration of adaptive engagement strategies, will set the stage for success in the upcoming phase.

9. Annex 1

This section outlines some examples of the Road Maps as developed from the technical Pilots of the MULTISOURCE projects, using as a guideline the structure described in the Chapter 3 Road Map Structure.

Road Runoff

Introduction to the roadmap

This document presents the roadmap for stakeholder engagement concerning the Multisource pilot in Oslo. The pilot consists of a nature-based treatment system for road run-off, which is being monitored for its effect on water quality.

The main objectives of the stakeholder engagement are to evaluate the co-benefits of the pilot, apart from its ability to treat polluted water, and to share knowledge and experience across different fields of professional and societal groups. This will be done through site visits, demonstrations, seminars and workshops.

Main purpose

Long Term Planning 2022-2025

Key objectives:

- Treatment of road run-off is an important issue, and this pilot is an excellent opportunity for the city to develop new knowledge and solutions.
- Communicate the results of our research and discuss what relevance the results might have for the local norms and regulations related to the topic. Water quality is essential, and we need to work together to define new regulations to ensure proper water treatment to improve the water quality in the urban water bodies.
- Feedback on co-benefits from professionals and local community: benefits, down-sides, priorities
- Engage students in practical research on urban, nature-based solutions.

Expected outcomes:

- New knowledge about the treatment of polluted road runoff in NBS
- A mapping of co-benefits for such solutions
- Dissemination of the results of the pilot project
- Discussions on local norms and regulations
- Student works using our pilot as a case

Short-Term Planning 2022-2023

Key objectives:

- Discuss the solutions used in the pilot, their function, co-benefits, and applicability in other contexts.
- Communicate the results of our research and discuss what the relevance of the results might have for the local norms and regulations related to the topic
- Share data, knowledge, and ideas, and look for synergies with other ongoing or future projects
- Inform the public/local community about the research being done

Expected outcomes:

- Discussions on water treatment and regulation in a seminar and during an on-site visit

- Evaluation of function and co-benefits of the pilot

Implementation Plan: Timeline of the Activities

Activities planned for the longer term:

- Engage school to include the pilot in educational program
- Involve professor/students from relevant fields of study (AHO or NMBU)
 - o Site visit
 - o Engage prof. to develop student assignment?
- Knowledge exchange group (using existing networks for storm and climate adaptation water in Oslo/Norway)
- Presentation in webinar (NIVAs webinar series on NBS?)

Short Term Planning 2022-2023

Activities planned for the next 12 months (to be filled into the form and time-line):

- Seminar (march) (NIVA)
 - o Aim: inform about the project, create networks, invite experts to discussions on the topic of NBS and water treatment
 - o Stakeholder: academia, public management, state authorities
- Site visit/practical demonstration (coordinate with official opening of the street?) (spring)
 - o Aim: inform, engage
 - o Stakeholder: politicians, management and project developers (neighbours?)
- Expert on-site workshop
 - o Aim: asses co-benefits
 - o Stakeholder: experts from municipality and research in different fields related to relevant co-benefit (biodiversity, walkability, universal access, traffic, street planning etc.)
- On-site information (is it possible to make it interactive?)
 - o Aim: inform the general population about the project and NBS
 - o Stakeholder: general population
- Dissemination of preliminary results in various presentations:
 - o Different forums within the municipality of Oslo
 - o Vegforum for byer og tettsteder (Road forum for cities and towns)

Figure 9. Short term planning for 2023, City of Oslo

The activities that have yet to be planned in detail are difficult to elaborate on. Therefore, in the table below, the activities that are planned are detailed. We can supplement with more information about several of the activities in due course:

Introduction to the activity	Title of the milestone/deliverable/main output				
	Seminar				
	Short description of the milestones/deliverables/main output (max 60 word)				
	Seminar on contaminated stormwater				
Co-design Framework for stakeholder engagement	Purpose for stakeholder engagement (Please select one of the following categories and specify the purpose of engagement on your context)				
	Documentation of the lessons learned	Sharing of knowledge and experience	Integration of experts' views	Evaluation of outcomes and outputs	
	The aim is to inform about the project, create networks, invite experts to discussions on the topic of NBS and water-treatment.				
	Group(s) of the stakeholders (Please consult the Stakeholder Engagement Process (I.e. Miro Boards) for your Pilot/Tool)				
	Academia, public management, state authorities				
	Method to engage (Please consult the list of methods to engage in this link, or add more)				
	Knowledge exchange groups				
Timeline	Period to engage with the stakeholders (Month)				
	March				
Logistics of the organisation	Leading organisation to develop the stakeholder engagement activity				
	NIVA				
	Potential synergies with other project partners				
	NIVA				
	Support from ICLEI (Please select the level of support from ICLEY and specify it based on your context)				
	Basic: Inform ICLEI on the activity development		Intermediate: Consult ICLEI on the activity development	Advanced: Co-develop the activity	
	Local/Regional/International Event to organize the stakeholder engagement activity as part of it				

Table 2. Seminar on contaminated stormwater

Pre-treated wastewater

Introduction

The pilot in Ypres will provide Rietland with new understanding on how well the Phytoparking performs in terms of removal efficiencies of the classical parameters, pathogens, metals, micro plastics and organic micro pollutants. The objective is to share this information in the short term with the knowledge stakeholders (Academia, government, Wetland community). This will hopefully lead to more understanding at governmental level which can lead to changes in Flemish legislation in regard to the reuse of effluent for irrigation and/or infiltration. The second objective is to inform the construction and touristic sector on this innovative technology and how to implement them in their future projects.

Main Purpose:

WHAT

- Gaining knowledge and insight into the operation of the Phytoparking
- Using knowledge to implement effluent reuse in legislation.
- Making Phytoparking more known to the construction and tourism sector

WHO

- Academia: University of Ghent, Wetland Community, VLAQWA (Flanders Knowledge Centre Water)
- Government: VMM (Flemish Environmental Agency), VVSG (umbrella organization for cities and municipalities)
- Private sector: Construction sector (developers, architects, contractors, investors, etc.) Touristic sector (owners of hotels, campsites and holiday parks)
- Other: Water utility De Watergroep

Long Term: 2022 – 2025

From 2021, we had annual meetings with VMM (Flemish Environmental Agency), Flemish knowledge partners (University of Ghent and VLAQWA) and the Water Utility De Watergroep to share the results of the Multi Source project. We hope to establish a transparent relation with the Environmental Agency and to impact the legislation as trusted partner. We will organize a webinar at the end of Multi Source to inform a wide audience and will specifically invite various legislator bodies from Belgium (Flanders and Brussels) and the Netherlands to encourage the discussion.

To inform the construction sector on this innovative technology, Rietland will provide a site visit and content for lessons to Build Wise.

Short Term: 2022 – 2023

Rietland will participate in various congresses (IWA Wetlands & WETPOL) to share the knowledge obtained by this project with the Wetland Community. This will also be documented in the deliverables factsheet and report at the end of Multi Source. Rietland will be annually present at fairs (Aquarama, Aqua Nederland) and network meetings (VLARIO dag, End event Vlaanderen Circulair) to inform the construction and touristic sector about the Phytoparking and other NBS. In addition, we will try to reach the touristic sectors during their sustainability events (Toerisme Vlaanderen, Westtoer). Rietland participates four times a year in platforms that encourage decentralized water treatment and uncover obstacles to implement innovative technologies in the construction sector.

Timeline of activities

Roadmap planning 2023 and project planning are to be found in annex (pdf)

Figure 10. Long term planning for 2022-2025, Rietland

Fig 1: Roadmap project planning
Short term planning of activities

Figure 11. Short term planning for 2023, Rietland

Introduction to the activity	Title of the Milestone/ Deliverable/Main Output		
	Informing Touristic Sector about Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions (ENTS)		
	Short description of the Milestones/ Deliverables/Main Outputs (max 60 words)		
Co-design Framework for stakeholder engagement (Available here)	Guests of hotels and B&B use more water on holiday than at home. This is why the touristic sector of West Flanders and VLAKWA (knowledge institute of water in Flanders) organized together an event with multiple presentations and a small fair. Rietland was present at the fair and network moment afterwards. <u>Activity: Knowledge exchange for group2</u>		
	Purpose for stakeholder engagement (Please select one of the following categories and specify the purpose of engagement on your context)		
	Documentation of the lessons learned	Sharing knowledge of experience	Integration of experts' views
Group(s) of the stakeholders (Please consult the Stakeholder Engagement Process (i.e. Miro Boards) for your Pilot/ Tool)			

	<u>Group 2</u> ; motivate tourism to implement this technology		
	Method to engage (Please consult the list of methods to engage in this link, or add more)		
	Activity: Knowledge exchange for group2: (involve and consult) when we are invited by the sector to 1) inform them on water scarcity and our ENTs, 2) become a trusted partner, 3) provide the space for the audience to voice opinion, 4) communicate new activities (technical, legislative, tests) and optimization.		
Timeline	Period to engage with the stakeholders (Month)		
(See above)	9 February 2023		
Logistics of the organisation	Leading organisation to develop the stakeholder engagement activity		
	VLAKWA and Westtoer (touristic organization of West Flanders) Both organizations know Rietland well so they invited us to the fair.		
	Potential synergies with other project partners		
	NO		
	Support from ICLEI (Please select the level of support from ICLEI and specify it based on your context)		
	Basic: Inform ICLEI on the activity development	Intermediate: Consult ICLEI on the activity development	Advanced: Co-develop the activity
	Local/ Regional/ International Event to organise the stakeholder engagement activity as part of it		

Table 3. Informing Touristic Sector about Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions (ENTS)

Introduction to the activity	Title of the Milestone/ Deliverable/Main Output			
	Annual Meeting to share technological insights of the project			
	Short description of the Milestones/ Deliverables/Main Outputs (max 60 words)			
	Activity: Knowledge exchange group 1 and group 2: Rietland organizes ones a year an online meeting to share the learned lessons of the previous year.			
Co-design Framework for stakeholder engagement (Available here)	Purpose for stakeholder engagement (Please select one of the following categories and specify the purpose of engagement on your context)			
	Documentation of the lessons learned	Sharing knowledge and experience	Integration of experts' views	Evaluation of outcomes and outputs
	Purpose to involve and consult the knowledge partners + interested stakeholders from ministry and construction sector.			
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Share knowledge: can black or grey effluent 1) meet EU irrigation standards, 2) be safely reused in HH or offices? 2) Involve governmental stakeholders via a discussion, what knowledge is needed to translate the EU directive in BE legislation? 3) Involve stakeholders from construction sector via discussion, what do you require to implement these technologies in new projects? 			

	<p>4) Action plan 2023:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. fine tuning oxygen via sensors b. presentation for group of specific stakeholders (government, VVSG, EMbuild, NAV, ...) c. Educations program for EMBuild 	
	<p>Group(s) of the stakeholders (Please consult the Stakeholder Engagement Process (i.e. Miro Boards) for your Pilot/ Tool)</p>	
	<p><u>Group 1</u>: wants to learn from this pilot in terms of treatment performance: Rietland, University of Ghent, Wetland community, Environmental Agency, Water utility</p> <p><u>Group 2</u>: Rietland wants to motivate other sectors to use this technology: Tourism and construction sector should implement these NBS more.</p>	
	<p>Method to engage (Please consult the list of methods to engage in this link, or add more)</p>	
	<p>Engaging format = knowledge exchange (involve and consult) in an annual meeting to 1) maintain a close dialogue, 2) become a trusted partner for the government, 3) provide the space for stakeholders to voice opinion, 4) communicate new activities (technical, legislative, tests) and optimization</p>	
Timeline	<p>Period to engage with the stakeholders (Month)</p>	
(See above)	<p>13 March 2023</p>	
Logistics of the organisation	<p>Leading organisation to develop the stakeholder engagement activity</p>	
	<p>Rietland supported by VLAKWA and UGent</p>	
	<p>Potential synergies with other project partners</p>	
	<p>H2pOzwer of VLAIO</p>	
	<p>Support from ICLEI (Please select the level of support from ICLEI and specify it based on your context)</p>	
	<p>Basic: Inform ICLEI on the activity development</p>	<p>Intermediate: Consult ICLEI on the activity development</p>
<p>Local/ Regional/ International Event to organise the stakeholder engagement activity as part of it</p>		

Table 4. Annual Meeting to share technological insights of the project

Combined Sewer Overflow

Timeline of activities

Long term planning for stakeholder engagement activities in 2022-2025

Mx: Main Output/ Deliverable/ Milestone

Stakeholder Engagement: Envisaged moments for engagement related to the Mx

CM: Consortium Meeting

Figure 12 Long Term Planning, Metropolitan Area of Milan

Short term planning for stakeholder engagement for 2023

	Title of the Milestone/ Deliverable/Main Output
	Setting up of the NBSWT metropolitan board
Focus of the engagement process	Short description of the Milestones/ Deliverables/Main Outputs (max 60 words)
	The goal is to establish an active, open and stable dialogue with those who are co-participating in bringing about change toward greener and more sustainable infrastructure, as well as to spread knowledge quickly and widely. During the meeting, membership was requested for a working table called the "NBSWT metropolitan board" to carry on a discussion on aspects and issues that characterize the topic of sustainable water management in our territory. The metropolitan board will meet semi-annually and will be involved in the qualifying processes within the MULTISOURCE project.
Implementation of the engagement process' (Guidance Available here)	Purpose for stakeholder engagement (Please specify the purpose of the stakeholder engagement as appropriate in your context)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing of knowledge and experience (from CMM and Iridra to the stakeholders) • maintain close dialogue with the stakeholders that make up the water resource management and use sector in the metropolitan area • serve as a collaborative platform to support and participate in the MULTISOURCE project activities

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide the space for stakeholder to voice opinion and communicate their interests in the 3 thematic tables selected • Identify issues that need to be addressed in the near future
Group(s) of the stakeholders (Please consult the Stakeholder Engagement Process (i.e. Miro Boards) for your Pilot/ Tool)
Some stakeholders from the core team group and some from the direct group
Method to engage (Please consult the list of methods to engage in this link, or add more)
Knowledge exchange groups

Table 5. Setting up of the NBSWT metropolitan board

10. References

- Petsani (2022) Co-design framework for stakeholder engagement in the Nature-Based Solution for Water Treatment. MULTISOURCE Deliverable 6.1, H2020 grant no. 101003527

The overall goal of MULTISOURCE is to, together with local, national, and international stakeholders, demonstrate a variety of about Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions (ENTS) treating a wide range of urban waters and to develop innovative tools, methods, and business models that support citywide planning and long-term operations and maintenance of nature-based solutions for water treatment, storage, and reuse in urban areas worldwide. The project includes seven pilots treating a wide range of urban waters. Two individual municipalities (Girona, Spain; Oslo, Norway), two metropolitan municipalities (Lyon, France; Milan, Italy), and international partners in Brazil, Vietnam, and the USA will contribute to each of the main project activities: ENTS pilots, risk assessment, business models, technology selection, and the MULTISOURCE Planning Platform. The use of urban archetypes in the Planning Platform will enable users to quickly classify regions (in both developed or developing countries) suitable for the application of nature-based solutions for water treatment (NBSWT) and compare scenarios both with and without NBSWT.

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